

A Hybrid Framework for Shape Registration with Affine and Block-Wise Quadratic Deformations

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Abstract Most existing Euclidean and affine-based registration methods remain insufficient for modeling complex nonlinear deformations. Building on existing affine registration methods, this paper proposes a hybrid affine-quadratic registration framework that combines affine-invariant global alignment with block-wise quadratic refinements to capture second-order geometric distortions. The approach ensures numerical stability through condition-number minimization of the equi-affine correspondence matrix and employs a closed-form least squares solution for global affine estimation, followed by Tikhonov-regularized least squares for stable quadratic refinements. The number of local deformation blocks is automatically selected using BIC. Experiments conducted on MPEG-7, Kimia-99, Kimia-216 and ETH-80 datasets demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed method in improving registration accuracy under complex shape variations.

Keywords: Shape registration, affine transformation, quadratic refinement, hybrid alignment, block-wise deformation.

1 Introduction

Planar curve registration concerns the estimation of a geometric transformation that aligns two parametric curves $\gamma_1, \gamma_2 : I \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^2$ representing the same underlying shape. It is a fundamental problem in computer vision and geometric data analysis, with applications including silhouette-based 3D reconstruction, medical image alignment [1], robot navigation, object tracking, and content-based image retrieval [2]. With the rise of real-time and perception-driven systems such as augmented and mixed reality, AR-assisted surgery, virtual try-on, autonomous vehicle localization, and aerial platforms, the need for accurate and efficient contour alignment has in-

tensified. Beyond global geometric models, registration methods can be broadly classified into parametric and non-parametric approaches [3]. Parametric methods assume an explicit functional form for the transformation with a finite set of parameters, such as affine, projective, or spline-based models. Non-parametric methods define transformations more flexibly through dense displacement fields or variational formulations, allowing highly expressive deformations but often at a higher computational cost. Classical non-rigid parametric frameworks include Thin Plate Spline (TPS) [4] and TPS-RPM [5], which provide smooth global deformations but are limited to low-dimensional point sets. Probabilistic methods, such as Coherent Point Drift (CPD) [6], regularize point displacements according to motion coherence theory and achieve smooth non-rigid alignment but rely on kernel-based smoothing. More flexible approaches, such as diffeomorphic methods, model large deformations via smooth invertible mappings, providing a mathematically rigorous framework for non-rigid registration [7]. Within affine-invariant geometric frameworks, Ghorbel et al. proposed the Affine Curve Matching Algorithm (ACMA), a robust and analytically grounded method for planar curve registration under affine transformations, with resilience to partial occlusion and incomplete contours [8,9]. However, although ACMA offers strong affine invariance and numerical stability, affine transformations remain insufficient to model the moderate nonlinear geometric distortions often encountered in practical imaging scenarios.

Building on and inspired by the ACMA framework, we propose a hybrid quadratic transformation model for planar curve registration. The proposed method extends the affine formulation by incorporating controlled second-order geometric terms within a finite-dimensional and fully explicit representation. A global affine component preserves invariance and stability, while block-wise quadratic refinements, applied locally [10] and selected using the Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC) [11], enable the modeling of moderate nonlinear deformations without resorting to dense displacement fields or kernel-based interpolation. The transformation parameters are estimated through a closed-form least-squares solution, ensuring analytical tractability and computational efficiency.

2 Quadratic transformation

A quadratic transformation known as a rubber-sheet deformation $f : \mathbb{R}^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^2$ at a point $u = (x, y)$ with a local offset $v = (h, k)$ can be locally approximated by:

$$f(u + v) \approx f(u) + J_f(u)v + \frac{1}{2}v^\top H_f(u)v, \quad (1)$$

where $J_f(u)$ and $H_f(u)$ denote the Jacobian and Hessian matrices, respectively.

In parametric form, the transformation reads:

$$P(h, k) = \begin{bmatrix} a_{00} + a_{10}h + a_{01}k + \frac{1}{2}a_{20}h^2 + a_{11}hk + \frac{1}{2}a_{02}k^2 \\ b_{00} + b_{10}h + b_{01}k + \frac{1}{2}b_{20}h^2 + b_{11}hk + \frac{1}{2}b_{02}k^2 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (2)$$

Intuition: The linear coefficients $(a_{10}, a_{01}, b_{10}, b_{01})$ correspond to classical affine operations such as translation, rotation, scaling, and shearing, while the quadratic coefficients $(a_{20}, a_{11}, a_{02}, b_{20}, b_{11}, b_{02})$ introduce curvature and local warping, enabling flexible nonlinear deformations.

Figure 1 summarizes the geometric effect of each quadratic coefficient along the x and y axes.

Figure 1 – Visual illustration of the geometric effects of individual quadratic terms in the polynomial warping model. Each subfigure shows the deformation of a regular grid when only the corresponding parameter is activated.

3 The proposed method

The proposed hybrid affine–quadratic framework extends classical affine matching by integrating structured local quadratic refinements to better capture non-linear shape variations. The method is composed of four main stages: (i) curve smoothing,

normalization, and arc-length reparameterization to ensure geometric consistency; (ii) global affine transformation estimation to model coarse alignment; (iii) block-wise residual quadratic refinement to account for localized non-linear deformations while preserving the global affine structure; and (iv) similarity evaluation based on a L_2 distance metric for retrieval and ranking.

Figure 2 – Illustration of the complete processing pipeline of the proposed hybrid affine-quadratic matching method

4 Evaluation experiments

This section evaluates the proposed registration algorithm through a comprehensive comparison with state-of-the-art methods, focusing on recognition, registration accuracy, and retrieval performance using the Bull’s Eye Score.

4.1 Shape registration applications

In the experiments, we conduct three types of tests [8] (whole-to-whole, part-to-whole, and part-to-part) to evaluate the performance of the proposed registration

algorithm on the following datasets: MPEG-7 (Fig. 3), Kimia-216 (Fig. 4), and ETH-80 (Fig. 5).

Figure 3 – Missed or Altered object registration on the MPEG-7 dataset: (a,b) initial curves; (c,d) original shape aligned with the registered shape

Figure 4 – Kimia216: (a,b) initial curves; (c,d) original shapes aligned with the registered shapes

Figure 5 – ETH-80: (a,b) initial curves; (c,d) original shapes aligned with the registered shapes

4.2 Alignment Error Calculation

Table 1 – Comparison of average registration errors on the Kimia-99 dataset.

Method	Average Registration Error (%)
ACMA [8]	9.35
AICD [12]	12.13
CSS_SW [13]	21.76
Proposed Algorithm	2.53

As shown in Table 1, the proposed algorithm achieved an average registration error of 2.53% on the Kimia-99 dataset, which is lower than the 9.35%, 12.13%, and 21.76% reported for ACMA [8], AICD [12], and CSS-SW [13], respectively. This demonstrates a significant improvement in registration accuracy over existing methods.

4.3 Image database retrieval

Table 2 presents the Bullseye Scores on the MPEG-7 Set B dataset. The proposed Affine and Local Quadratic Refinement achieves competitive performance (96.54%), closely approaching the best reported result (97.31%) obtained by IDSC + DDGM + co-transduction. Unlike this graph-based and transductive approach, which is computationally intensive, our method relies on direct geometric refinement, offering a better balance between retrieval accuracy and computational efficiency.

Table 2 – Comparison on MPEG-7 Set B dataset (Bullseye Score).

Method	Bullseye (%)
Visual parts [14]	76.45
SC + TPS [15]	76.51
CSS_SW [13]	81.33
AICD [12]	84.26
HF [16]	89.66
ACMA [8]	91.55
LCDP [17]	93.32
IDSC + DDGM + Co-transduction [18]	97.31
Ours (Affine + Local Quadratic Refinement)	96.54

5 Conclusion

This work proposes a hybrid affine–quadratic model for planar curve registration, effectively addressing moderately nonlinear deformations. The experiments demonstrate improved robustness and accuracy compared to existing methods. Future work could focus on extending the approach to 3D shapes and handling more complex deformations.

References

1. Xiaofeng Cao, Jiayuan Fan, Peng Dong, S. Ahmad, Pew-Thian Yap, and Dinggang Shen. Image registration using machine and deep learning. In *Handbook of Medical Image Computing and Computer Assisted Intervention*, pages 319–342. Elsevier, 2020.
2. Y. Yang et al. Deep learning for shape matching and registration: A survey. *IEEE TPAMI*, 2021.
3. Hao Zhu, Bin Guo, Ke Zou, Yongfu Li, Ka-Veng Yuen, Lyudmila Mihaylova, and Henry Leung. A review of point set registration: From pairwise registration to groupwise registration. *Sensors*, 19(5):1191, 2019.
4. Fred L. Bookstein. Principal warps: Thin-plate splines and the decomposition of deformations. *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence*, 11(6):567–585, June 1989.
5. H. Chui and A. Rangarajan. A new point matching algorithm for non-rigid registration: Tps-rpm. *Computer Vision and Image Understanding*, 89(2-3):114–141, 2003.
6. Andriy Myronenko and Xubo Song. Point set registration: Coherent point drift. *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence*, 32(12):2262–2275, December 2010.
7. M. F. Beg, M. I. Miller, A. Trouvé, and L. Younes. Computing large deformation metric mappings via geodesic flows of diffeomorphisms. *International Journal of Computer Vision*, 61:139–157, 2005.
8. Gideon E. Schwarz. Estimating the dimension of a model. *The Annals of Statistics*, 6(2):461–464, 1978.
9. Sinda Elghoul and Faouzi Ghorbel. A fast and robust affine-invariant method for shape registration under partial occlusion. *International Journal of Multimedia Information Retrieval*, 11:39–59, 2022.
10. K. Joshi and M. I. Patel. Recent advances in local feature detector and descriptor: A literature survey. *International Journal of Multimedia Information Retrieval*, 9:1–17, 2020.
11. Gideon E. Schwarz. Estimating the dimension of a model. *The Annals of Statistics*, 6(2):461–464, 1978.
12. H. Fu, Z. Tian, M. Ran, and M. Fan. Novel affine-invariant curve descriptor for curve matching and occluded object recognition. *IET Computer Vision*, 7(4):279–292, 2013.
13. F. Mai, C. Q. Chang, and Y. S. Hung. Affine-invariant shape matching and recognition under partial occlusion. In *2010 IEEE International Conference on Image Processing (ICIP)*, pages 4605–4608. IEEE, 2010.
14. L. J. Latecki, R. Lakamper, and T. Eckhardt. Shape descriptors for non-rigid shapes with a single closed contour. In *Proceedings of the IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR)*, pages 424–429. IEEE, 2000.
15. Greg Mori, Serge Belongie, and Jitendra Malik. Efficient shape matching using shape contexts. *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence*, 27(11):1832–1837, 2005.
16. Jun Wang, Xiang Bai, Xinge You, Wenyu Liu, and Longin Jan Latecki. Shape matching and classification using height functions. *Pattern Recognition Letters*, 33(2):134–143, 2012.
17. Xiang Yang, Selen Koknar-Tezel, and Longin Jan Latecki. Locally constrained diffusion process on locally densified distance spaces with applications to shape retrieval. In *Proceedings of the IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR)*, pages 357–364, 2009.
18. Xiang Bai, Bo Wang, Cong Yao, Wenyu Liu, and Zhuowen Tu. Co-transduction for shape retrieval. *IEEE Transactions on Image Processing*, 21(5):2747–2757, May 2012.